

INFLUENCE OF PLY THICKNESS ON THE FIBRE MATRIX DEBONDING

Christian Leopold¹, Wilfried V. Liebig¹, Sergej Harder¹ and Bodo Fiedler¹

¹Institute of Polymer Composites, Technical University Hamburg-Harburg
Denickestraße 15, D-21073 Hamburg, Germany

Email: christian.leopold@tuhh.de, wilfried.liebig@tuhh.de, sergej.harder@tuhh.de
fiedler@tuhh.de,

Web page: www.tuhh.de/kvweb

Keywords: Model composite, Finite element method (FEM), Micromechanics, Glass fibres

ABSTRACT

In this work, the influence of ply thickness in the 90° layer in cross-ply laminates on the initiation of fibre matrix debonding and inter-fibre-fracture under tensile loads is investigated experimentally by using model composites as well as in a FEM simulation. Decreasing the ply thickness leads to a shift of the onset of inter-fibre-fracture to higher loads. The failure propagation at higher loads is less severe with decreasing layer thickness. Explanations for this behaviour like the probability of a critical defect in the reduced volume or the in-situ effect are discussed. The FEM model is able to represent the ply thickness effect and simulation results are qualitatively in good agreement with the experiments. In the simulation, first fibre-matrix-debonding was found at higher global strain and matrix cracks were more but less severe for thinner plies, whereas an earlier damage onset and fewer cracks, running through the whole layer thickness are found for thicker layers. A reduction of ply thickness in cross-ply laminates increases the resistance against inter-fibre-fracture and failure propagation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Introducing the load in fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) requires a tailored laminate design taking into account that multiaxial stresses occur. The onset of damage in multidirectional FRPs controlling the design is the matrix cracking in the 90° layers. One of the reasons for the initiation of matrix cracks and typically the first type of damage occurring in fibre-reinforced composites (FRP) is fibre-matrix debonding. The change in stiffness between fibres and matrix results in stress concentrations at the interface. Due to these stress concentrations fibre matrix debonding occurs, which leads to the initiation of matrix cracks, so called inter-fibre-fracture (IFF). Cracks in the matrix run along these debonded areas. IFF is the controlling failure criterion for design in many composite applications in aircraft or wind industry [1]. This type of damage is therefore of particular interest for understanding the damage mechanisms and for optimising the material with regard to mechanical properties. Strengthening of the fibre matrix interface or relieving stress concentrations of it, e.g. by nanoparticle modification in the matrix, may enhance mechanical properties and lifetime of composite parts because the initial onset of damage may be delayed to higher strains or a higher number of loading cycles respectively [2].

1.1 Influence of ply thickness

One approach for suppression of IFF is reducing the ply thickness of the laminate. The influence of ply thickness on the onset of delamination at the free edges is discussed since the 1980s [3]. Developments in the manufacturing technology during the last ten years allow production of UD-prepregs with a thickness of less than 20 µm. In comparison to conventional plies they are called thin-ply. Experimental results for thin-ply laminates with a thickness of less than 50 µm, first presented by Sihm et al. [4], show great potential in the suppression of matrix cracking. The thin-ply laminates made of prepregs produced by a tow spreading technology exhibit higher unnotched tensile strength in static and fatigue loading as well as higher compressive strength. Other research groups report similar

behaviour: reducing the ply thickness leads to a delay in the onset of damage to higher loads [5–8]. One explanation for this behaviour is that with the reduction of the ply volume, the probability that this ply contains a critical defect for damage initiation is reduced, similar to the volume effect in fibres [8]. Furthermore, the influence of fibre orientation of the adjacent layers has an increasing influence on the in-situ effect of a layer with decreasing layer thickness. The in-situ effect describes an increase in transverse strength of a ply when it is constrained by plies of different fibre orientation and thus different stiffness. As was shown experimentally and analytically, the in-situ strengths of a ply in a laminate depend on its thickness [9–12], its position within the laminate [13] as well as on the orientation of the adjacent layers [10]. Thus, the in-situ strength also has an influence on the crack propagation in this ply, as was shown with a micromechanical FEM simulation for thin plies by Arteiro et al. [14]. The formation of fibre matrix debonding and initiation of IFF is investigated micromechanically with a multi-scale approach simulation using the finite element method (FEM) and an experimental test campaign with model composites. Model composites are used to reduce the total volume of the specimen and to investigate the damage initiation and propagation selectively in a small volume. This approach was already successfully used to analyse matrix cracking and fibre matrix load transfer [15], first ply failure [16], glass fibre-epoxy interfacial transverse strength [17] and the influence of voids on fibre matrix debonding and damage propagation [18]. The results obtained with the simulation are compared with experimental results. The influence of the 90° ply thickness in (0°/90°/0°) model composite laminates on the initiation and propagation of transverse cracks under quasi-static tensile loads is analysed under transmission light microscopy.

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Model composites are produced with glass fibre rovings in an epoxy matrix. E-glass fibre rovings *Hybon 2002* with a silane sizing from PPG Fiber Glass are used. Nominal roving tex is 600 g/km with a fibre diameter of 12 µm. The fibres have a tensile strength of 2290 MPa according to the data sheet. Momentive Epoxy Resin RIMR 135 with the hardener RIMH 137 is used as the matrix system.

In order to investigate the effect of ply thickness in the model composites, the width and the thickness of the rovings used as fibrous reinforcement were varied. Some specimens were manufactured using the rovings as delivered. The roving width is between 2.5 mm and 3.0 mm, the thickness is approximately 130-150 µm. A part of the roving was spread between two rollers of a three roll mill from Exakt Advanced Technologies GmbH. The gap between the rollers was set to 100 µm with a ratio of rotational speed of 30:10. Due to the difference in rotation speed, shear loads are introduced into the roving, but with the chosen set of parameters no damage of the fibres was detected in light microscopy analysis carried out after the spreading. The rovings were spread to a median width of 3.84 mm (+40 %), the thickness decreases about 30 % up to 100 µm. Model composites are produced with a casting setup, shown schematically in Figure 1. The fibre rovings are placed in the centre of a silicone mould. The resin and hardener are mixed according to the manufacturer's specification and degassed under vacuum. The matrix is infused via channels in the mould. The specimen are cured at room temperature in the mould for 24 h, demoulded and cured for 16 h at 80°C in an oven. Void free specimens with the dimensions given in Figure 1 were produced.

Figure 1: Scheme of the casting setup for manufacturing of model composites (left) and specimen geometry (right)

A crucifix-shape, introduced by Ogihara et al. [17] to evaluate the glass fibre/epoxy interfacial transverse strength, is chosen for specimen geometry to avoid early failure due to stress increase at the specimen edges and assure damage initiation in the centre ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) section of the specimen, where damage initiation and propagation is observed under transmission light microscopy. In addition, specimen with single glass fibres (three in 0° direction, seven in 90° direction) with a diameter of $72\ \mu\text{m}$ instead of the fibre rovings were produced with the same method. These are hereafter referred to as single-fibre specimen.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

The model composites are tested in a custom-made tensile test rig equipped with an extensometer and a load cell with a maximum load of 2 kN. The rig was positioned under a transmission light microscope. Load and displacement were continuously measured and recorded. The test was carried out at a constant crosshead speed of 0.03 mm/min. The fracture initiation and propagation was monitored on a screen. The test arrangement is shown schematically in Figure 2

Figure 2: Scheme of the test arrangement: a) Monitor for microscopy, b) Microscope, c) Monitor for force-displacement signal d) Tensile test rig with force and displacement sensor e) Test rig controller

4 RESULTS

Specimens are loaded continuously and initiation of damage is observed in-situ in transmission light microscopy. Fibre-matrix-debonding is observed in the single-fibre specimen to occur at the 90° fibre edges located in load direction. With the chosen geometry, fibre matrix debonding initiates in the centre of the specimen, as already described by Ogihara et al. [17]. In the roving specimen, obviously no fibre matrix debonding could be detected, but the onset of inter-fibre-fracture is clearly visible in the microscope. In Figure 3 and Figure 4 characteristic load-time diagrams for specimens with as-received and spread rovings respectively are given. In the diagrams, the failure propagation in a representative specimen under static tensile loading is presented at certain characteristic loads. First inter-fibre-fracture occurs at higher loads in the spread-roving specimens. Differences in the damage propagation are observed as well. Referring to Figure 3 and Figure 4, matrix cracks at a load above 800 N are smaller and shorter in the spread-roving specimens. The load at the first visible matrix crack is noted for each specimen. The results are shown in Figure 5, in which the applied load at the first visible matrix crack over the roving width is plotted.

Figure 3: Representative load-test time diagram for a model composite made of 2.5 mm wide rovings (no spreading) with images taken at different stages of damage.

Figure 4: Representative load-test time diagram for a model composite made of 3.85 mm wide spread-rovings with images taken at different stages of damage.

Figure 5: Tensile load at first visible matrix crack for ($0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$) model composite containing glass fibre rovings of different width

Figure 5 shows a clear trend: with increasing roving width, the load, at which first matrix cracking occurs, increases as well. For the specimen made with the rovings as delivered (roving width < 3.00 mm), a load at initial matrix cracks of $371 \text{ N} \pm 116 \text{ N}$ is measured. For the specimen containing spread rovings (roving width > 3.75 mm) the onset of the first matrix crack is shifted to a higher external load of $621 \text{ N} \pm 99 \text{ N}$ (refer to Figure 5). The maximum tensile strength of the tested specimen is $1539 \text{ N} \pm 213 \text{ N}$. No significant influence of the roving width on final failure is visible. Since the maximum tensile strength is dominated by the fibres in 0° direction, the initiation of matrix cracks have no high influence on the load at final failure in the tested configuration. The maximum tensile strength is influenced by several factors such as a possible deviation of the fibres in load direction from the 0° -axis or small variations in the manufacturing process. As can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4, in which the damage short before final failure in representative specimens for rovings with a width below and above 3 mm respectively is shown, multiple matrix cracks between the fibres in the 90° -direction as well as fibre breakage (FB) of the 0° fibres occur. There is a saturation in the number of matrix cracks after which the damage propagation continues first as broadening and prolongation of the existing cracks and finally as fibre breakage. Ultimate failure initiates in a region where a high amount of fibres in 0° -direction are broken by a crack transverse to the loading direction, separating the specimen next to the broadening of the cross section. As the cross section is the smallest and due to the specimen geometry, higher stresses per unit area and final failure was expected to occur in these regions.

5 MODELLING

For conducting the FEM simulation the commercial Software *Ansys Mechanical APDL 16.0* is used. The model is created in a parameter based approach. In a first step, a representative volume element (RVE) is created, containing the geometry of a single fibre with the fibre matrix interface and the surrounding matrix. An eight-node solid element with three degrees of freedom for each node is selected for the matrix and the fibre. For the fibre matrix interface, cohesive zone elements (CZE) with a bilinear model are chosen, which allow separation of the matrix from the fibre. This approach is described by Koyanagi et al. [19] for glass fibres and was already successfully used for a 2D FEM-analysis of crack suppression mechanisms in carbon fibre reinforced polymers by Saito et al. [20]. The traction of the cohesive zone elements is set to 50 MPa and the critical energy release rate

is 0.0055 N/mm in normal direction and 0.011 N/mm in tangential direction. The 90°-layer is created by merging the RVEs into the desired volume. A quadratic fibre arrangement is selected for the 90°-layer. This is a simplification, but allows analysis of damage initiation and general damage propagation mechanisms while significantly reducing calculation time. In future work, more realistic, randomly distributed fibres will be implemented in the model. The 0°-layer is modelled as a homogeneous material with the mechanical properties calculated with the rules of mixture. Figure 6 shows the approach for creating the model, the boundary conditions as well as layup and dimensions. Due to symmetry only one eighth of the composite layup is modelled. The length l , width w and thickness t_{0° of the homogeneous layer are kept constant, so only the thickness of the 90°-layer t_{ply} is varied. Because of the chosen symmetry (refer to Figure 6) the thickness t_{ply} in the model corresponds to a twice as high composite layer thickness. The coordinate system is set with the x-axis in direction of the 0°-fibres, the y-axis in thickness direction, leaving the z-axis in width direction.

Figure 6: Modelling approach for a (0°/90°/0°) cross-ply laminate with a) chosen symmetry (marked in red), b) dimensions and build-up and c) displacement and boundary conditions

The mechanical properties of fibre, matrix and the homogeneous 0°-layer are given in Table 1. Non-linear stress-strain matrix behaviour, with a linear elastic section at low strains, using the material data from Fiedler et al. [21] is implemented.

	E in GPa	ν in -	Strain at failure in %	G in GPa
Fibre	72.00	0.20	-	30.00
Matrix	3.93	0.39	5.65	1.40
0°-layer	31.16	0.31	2.00	2.26

Table 1: Material properties for fibre and matrix in the 90° layer and the homogenised 0°-layer

A constant displacement u is applied on the model in x-direction from 0 to 2 % global strain. At an increment of 0.1 % strain, failure of the CZEs as well as local strain in the matrix elements is analysed. If the separation in a CZE reaches its maximum value, the element fails. For the matrix, the elements reaching maximum tensile strain of the material are indicated as failed.

Figure 8 shows the failed CZEs at increasing strain from 1.7 %, the strain at which the first CZEs fail in the thickest configuration with 51 μm 90°-layer thickness, up to 2.0 % for the different ply thicknesses. As CZE failure corresponds to debonding of the fibre from the matrix, location, amount

and strain of fibre matrix debonding in relation to ply thickness can be analysed. The first fibre matrix debonding is located between the fibres. For thinner plies, initial fibre matrix debonding occurs at higher strains. In the 51 μm thick layer the first fibre matrix debonding can be seen at a strain of 1.7 %, whereas this is shifted to a strain of 1.8 % for the 34 μm thick layer and to 1.9 % for the thinnest 17 μm 90°-layer. In this layer, at eight regions failed CZE are found at a strain of 2 %, in the thick 51 μm layer only in four regions failed CZE can be identified at the same strain. Thus, with decreasing ply thickness fibre matrix debonding is spread more widely within the width, whereas for thicker layers, fibre matrix debonding occurs in less many but larger regions. In the diagram in Figure 7 the number of failed CZEs in relation to the total amount of CZE is plotted over applied global strains from 1.6 % to 2.0 % for the regarded ply thicknesses.

In the following, the damage propagation in the matrix is analysed. The strain of the matrix elements at an applied global strain between 1.7 % and 2 % for the different ply thicknesses is presented in Figure 9. Matrix elements reaching the maximum tensile strain of the matrix material appear in white and are assumed as failed. In the used nonlinear material model, the stress in these elements no longer increases after reaching the failure strain, but is held constant at the stress at this strain value (ideal plastic). In future work, matrix failure will be implemented. At first, the highest matrix strains are at the location of the fibre matrix debonding between the fibres. The failed CZEs no longer transfer load between fibre and matrix, therefore areas of higher matrix strain are shifted from between the fibres to the 6 and 12 o'clock position of the fibres. Matrix failure occurs at lower strains in the thicker plies. Paths of failed matrix run along the debonded area through the thickness of the 90°-layer transverse to the loading direction. In the thinnest 17 μm layer matrix failure is visible at several fibres, but there seem to be no cracks running through the whole 90°-layer thickness at 2.0 % applied strain. In the 34 μm thick layer six, and in the 51 μm thick layer four regions with cracking paths through the matrix can be identified. Thus, in thinner layers a higher amount of, but less severe (smaller and shorter) matrix cracks occur, whereas in the thicker layers only a few cracks running through the whole thickness are visible in the matrix.

Figure 7: Number of failed cohesive zone elements in relation to the total number of CZE in the ply at an applied global strain between 1.6 % and 2.0 % for different the ply thickness

Figure 8: Failed cohesive zone elements between fibre and matrix for different ply thickness at global applied strain from 1.7 % to 2.0 %

Figure 9: Equivalent matrix strain in different ply thicknesses for an applied global strain between 1.7% and 2.0%

6 DISCUSSION

With increasing roving width, a shift of the onset of IFF to higher loads is found. With the spreading of the rovings, the thickness of the fibre layers in the model composite is reduced. A decreasing layer thickness leads to higher initial failure loads. This is in good agreement with previous investigations on the ply thickness effect from other authors [4–8]. Despite the possibility of having a critical defect, is smaller in the thinner layers, the in-situ strength is an explanation for the observed phenomena. The transverse shear strength of the 90°-layer between two adjacent 0°-layers is higher for decreasing layer thickness. This is in good agreement with the simulation results, in which the experimentally observed shift of IFF to higher global strains is found as well. More, but less severe matrix cracks in the 90°-plies occur with reduced ply thickness, which was shown by other authors in FEM [14,20] and is confirmed by our own simulation. This is in agreement with the experimental results. It was found, that at approximately 50 % of the maximum tensile load, the matrix cracks are broader and more elongated for a higher layer thickness. Crack initiation and propagation is comparable with FEM of CFRP [20]. The ply thickness effect is clearly visible even in hand casted roving model composite. In the small volume, a more detailed failure process of the 90°-layer is visible compared to different normative specimen sizes. The simulation results are qualitatively in good agreement with the experiments. The crack initiation and propagation is restricted by the neighbouring 0°-layers carrying most of the load.

7 CONCLUSION

The model is able to represent the ply thickness effect and simulation results with regard to the effect of ply thickness on IFF are qualitatively in good agreement with the experiments. Decreasing the ply thickness leads to a shift of the onset of inter-fibre-fracture to higher loads, as first fibre-matrix-debonding occurs at higher global strain and damage development in the form of matrix cracks occurs in more regions but is less severe for thinner plies. Concluding one can say that a reduction of ply thickness in cross-ply laminates increases the resistance against inter-fibre-fracture and thus results in an increased fatigue lifetime. The results obtained from the test with model composites show the interdependency of decreasing ply thickness and IFF, hereby confirming the results from literature about industrial thin-ply laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank EXAKT Advanced Technologies GmbH for offering the possibilities for the spreading of the rovings.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hosoi, S. Sakuma, Y. Fujita, H. Kawada, Prediction of initiation of transverse cracks in cross-ply CFRP laminates under fatigue loading by fatigue properties of unidirectional CFRP in 90° direction, *Composites Part A*, **68**, (Complete) 2015, pp. 398–405 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.10.022).
- [2] J. B. Knoll, B. T. Riecken, N. Kosmann, S. Chandrasekaran, K. Schulte, B. Fiedler, The effect of carbon nanoparticles on the fatigue performance of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **67**, (0) 2014, pp. 233–40 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.022).
- [3] R. Y. Kim, S. R. Soni, Experimental and Analytical Studies On the Onset of Delamination in Laminated Composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **18**, (1) 1984, pp. 70–80 (doi:10.1177/002199838401800106).
- [4] S. Sihm, R. Y. Kim, K. Kawabe, S. W. Tsai, Experimental studies of thin-ply laminated composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, (6) 2007, pp. 996–1008 (doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.06.008).
- [5] T. Yokozeiki, Y. Aoki, T. Ogasawara, Experimental characterization of strength and damage resistance properties of thin-ply carbon fiber/toughened epoxy laminates, *Composite Structures*, **82**, (3) 2008, pp. 382–9 (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2007.01.015).
- [6] H. Saito, M. Morita, K. Kawabe, M. Kanasaki, H. Takeuchi, M. Tanaka et al., Effect of ply-thickness on impact damage morphology in CFRP laminates, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **30**, (13) 2011, pp. 1097–106 (doi:10.1177/0731684411416532).
- [7] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, P. P. Camanho, Large damage capability of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **63**, (0) 2014, pp. 110–22 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.04.002).
- [8] R. Amacher, J. Cugnoni, J. Botsis, L. Sorensen, W. Smith, C. Dransfeld, Thin ply composites: Experimental characterization and modeling of size-effects, *Composites Science and Technology*, **101**, (0) 2014, pp. 121–32 (doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.06.027).
- [9] A. Parvizi, K. W. Garrett, J. E. Bailey, Constrained cracking in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy cross-ply laminates, *J Mater Sci*, **13**, (1) 1978, pp. 195-201 (doi:10.1007/BF00739291).
- [10] D. L. Flaggs, M. H. Kural, Experimental Determination of the In Situ Transverse Lamina Strength in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **16**, (2) 1982, pp. 103–16 (doi:10.1177/002199838201600203).
- [11] A. Parvizi, J. E. Bailey, On multiple transverse cracking in glass fibre epoxy cross-ply laminates, *J Mater Sci*, **13**, (10) 1978, pp. 2131-2136 (doi:10.1007/BF00541666).
- [12] T. A. Sebaey, J. Costa, P. Maimí, Y. Batista, N. Blanco, J. A. Mayugo, Measurement of the in situ transverse tensile strength of composite plies by means of the real time monitoring of microcracking, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **65**, (0) 2014, pp. 40–6 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.02.001).

- [13] P. P. Camanho, C. G. Dávila, S. T. Pinho, L. Iannucci, P. Robinson, Prediction of in situ strengths and matrix cracking in composites under transverse tension and in-plane shear, *CompTest 2004*, **37**, (2) 2006, pp. 165–76 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.04.023).
- [14] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, A. R. Melro, P. Linde, P. P. Camanho, Micro-mechanical analysis of the in situ effect in polymer composite laminates, *Composite Structures*, **116**, (0) 2014, pp. 827–40 (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.06.014).
- [15] B. Fiedler, K. Schulte, Photo-elastic analysis of fibre-reinforced model composite materials, *6th International Conference On Composite Interfaces*, **57**, (8) 1997, pp. 859–67 (doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(96)00177-7).
- [16] B. Fiedler, C. de Jong, T. Hobbiebrunken, M. Hojo, K. Schulte, Micro/macro-mechanical approach of first ply failure in CFRP, *J Mater Sci*, **41**, (20) 2006, pp. 6760–7 (doi:10.1007/s10853-006-0215-4).
- [17] S. Ogihara, Y. Sakamoto, J. Koyanagi, Evaluation of Interfacial Tensile Strength in Glass Fiber/Epoxy Resin Interface using the Cruciform Specimen Method, *JMMP*, **3**, (9) 2009, pp. 1071–80 (doi:10.1299/jmmp.3.1071).
- [18] W. V. Liebig, C. Leopold, K. Schulte, Photoelastic study of stresses in the vicinity of a unique void in a fibre-reinforced model composite under compression, *Composites Science and Technology*, **84**, (0) 2013, pp. 72–7 (doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.04.011).
- [19] J. Koyanagi, P. D. Shah, S. Kimura, S. K. Ha, H. Kawada, Mixed-Mode Interfacial Debonding Simulation in Single-Fiber Composite under a Transverse Load, *Journal of Solid Mechanics and Materials Engineering*, **3**, (5) 2009, pp. 796–806 (doi:10.1299/jmmp.3.796).
- [20] H. Saito, H. Takeuchi, I. Kimpara, A study of crack suppression mechanism of thin-ply carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer laminate with mesoscopic numerical simulation, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **48**, (17) 2014, pp. 2085–96 (doi:10.1177/0021998313494430).
- [21] B. Fiedler, M. Hojo, S. Ochiai, K. Schulte, M. Ochi, Finite-element modeling of initial matrix failure in CFRP under static transverse tensile load, *Composites Science and Technology*, **61**, (1) 2001, pp. 95–105 (doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(00)00198-6).